

VOCATION OF POLITICS AND SOCIAL STATUS: A TECHNICAL STUDY OF NIGERIA'S 'OLD' AND 'NEW' YOUTHS**ADELEKE, Gabriel Osulale**

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Abstract:

People choose politics as their vocation either for pursuing a cause for societal advancement or their selfish economic interests. Where the second option predominates, the welfare of the citizens remains retrograde. The paper examined the relationships between old youths' access to power and upward social mobility it accrued to them by taking politics as a vocation and the reactions of new youths to the way the old youths use power in their possession. The study employed systematic criticism as its methodology, given its value of the continuous processes of critical discussion of alternative views in the resolution of societal problems. The paper revealed that there was a problem of status inconsistency between the old and new youths, occasioned by the selfish economic benefits of old youths who today are Nigerian leaders. This resulted in antagonistic reactions from new youths to challenge their status inconsistency as manifested in their limited upward social mobility when they compared their youthful time with the similar time of the old youths. Though certain socio-political advantages came, the antagonistic reactions of the new youths produced far-reaching negative impacts on the nation's sustainable development, hence the need for mechanisms to remove their status inconsistency. It is suggested, inter alia, that our socialization should seek for holistic understanding of the environment incorporating the knowledge to exploit and the wisdom to distribute, and that there is need to develop sense of community that incorporates universal golden rule, logic of utilitarianism and rule of humanity.

Keywords: Politics, Social Status, Stratification, Vocation, Youths.**Introduction**

Certain set of people take politics as their vocation, which is simply defined as a strong feeling of suitability for a particular career or occupation (Advanced English Dictionary). It is linked to the phenomenon of occupation "as business, trade, etc., that which occupies one's time permanently or as a hobby; a means of livelihood" and not defined in terms of motivation "primarily by consideration of pay, promotion, job-security, concern for good condition of service, and other self-regarding interests" (Adekanye, 1993: 3). According to Max Weber

(file:///C:/Users/USER/Desktop/Weber%20Politics%20as%20a%20Vocation.pdf), there are two ways of making politics one's vocation: He who lives 'for' politics makes politics his life, in an internal sense. Either he enjoys the naked possession of the power he exerts, or he nourishes his balance and self-feeling by the consciousness that his life has meaning in the service of a 'cause'. He who strives to make politics as a permanent source of income lives 'off' politics as a vocation.

In times and locations, some families or individuals choose politics as their vocation, and are called politicians and their ideal role is actively engaging in conducting

the business of government (Adegoruwa, 2020). There have been Du Valliers of Haiti, the Kennedys of United States of America, the Oxford and Cambridge families of United Kingdom, to mention just a few (Bolaji, 1980). Recently, the Bush and Clintons families are examples in the United States of America. In Nigeria, examples include Obafemi Awolowo, Nnamdi Azikwe, Ahmadu Bello, Tafawa Balewa, Shehu Shagari and Okoti Eboh, Olusegun Obasanjo, Bola Ige, Shehu Musa Yar'Adua, Abubakar Atiku, Olusegun Osoba, Olusola Saraki, Bukola Saraki, Gbemisola Saraki, Ibrahim Kwakanso, Bola Hammed Tinubu, and several others.

Those who choose politics as their vocation desire power, and a functional role of power is that it is about making decisions to determine, preserve and amend the general rules under which people live, advance, and reproduce the human social existence (Leftwich, 2004). As power accrues many advantages to its holders, the behaviour, attitudes, policies and programmes of power holders towards public welfare explain the type to which they belong in Max Weber's classification, '*for politics*' or '*off politics*'.

Many people however disdain politics as an immoral activity that should be avoided for corruption, election rigging, assassination, insecurity of life and property now constitute the order of the day in Nigeria (Odumuyiwa, 2008). Some others deride politics due to their real or imaginary conception of the failure of government in terms of what government ought to do or ought not to do in respect of a certain problem or issue of public implication (Magbadelo, 2006). But these are not enough to totally abandon politics for the fact that access to power has its essential goals which include the advancement and reproduction of social life, including occupation of important political offices of the state and enjoyment of perks and preferments of office (Aiyede, 2021). Many a people have used political power to enhance the general welfare of the people and their status in the society, and many for their selfish ends.

Therefore, political power is never an end in itself but a means to other ends as they were able to elevate their societies above others, and even themselves above not only other people, but their peers, families and other associates in time and space. In Nigeria,

through the privileges that old youths got from making politics as their vocation, they have come to assume pivotal positions in the worlds of trade, and commerce, agriculture, hotel business, shipping, aviation, building private universities, owning radio and television stations and newspaper proprietorships like the defunct *West African Pilot* of Dr. Nnamdi Azikwe, *Nigerian Tribune* of Chief Obafemi Awolowo, and *The Nation*, Television Continental and Max FM broadcast stations of Bola Hammed Tinubu etc. This translates to they have enjoyed upward social mobility through political power.

Recent studies concerning youth crises have blamed the factors on youths' frustrating conditions socially, politically, economically and otherwise (Akande and Okowa, 2009; Okunola, 2013; Toriola, 2017; Hammed, 2024). While their claims are right, however, specific attention to reactions to status inconsistency, its trivial gain and wide-ranging negative consequences on the nation's development, especially applying Tumin's (1967) various ways by which groups react to symbolized inferiority, has not received much attention in the study of crises of youths in Nigeria's fourth republic. For instance, Okunola (2013) revealed that globally youths feel deprived of adequate education and unemployment. However, a critical look at Nigerian scenario of youth crises depicts much, though not wholly, a case of educational opportunities without enough employment opportunities. This brings to fore the problem of status inconsistency in Nigeria's youth crises.

For analytical purpose, Nigerian youths are divided into old and new, old being group of people who were within the age bracket of 18-40 at the time of Nigeria's 1960 independence to 1970 while the new youth being Nigerians who are in the same age bracket during Nigeria's 3rd military era (1984-1999) and fourth republic (1999-date). In general terms, the study intends to explain the relationships between people's access to power and upward social mobility it accrues to those who make politics as their vocation in Nigeria. Specifically, it assesses the impact of the possession of power on socio-economic status of old youths who have had access to power and how they have behaved in terms of welfare of the people, especially the new

youths in Nigeria. It also examined the reactions of 'new youths' to status inconsistency, based on Tumin (1967) techniques of reactions to status inconsistency, caused in parts by the introduction of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1987 and exploitative political modus of old youths on their welfare. Furthermore, it surveyed the socio-economic implications of the reactions of the new youths to status inconsistency on the nation's development. The paper is ended with conclusion and suggestions.

Conceptual Understanding

Social stratification is regarded by social scientists as a whole gamut of phenomena like social inequalities, differentiation, class, ranking, evaluation, rewarding, and mobility. Social status is a product of social stratification and derives its meaning in it. For Hanneman (1984), social stratification includes three basic processes, namely:

- (i) the **distributive** processes, concerned with the resources of material wealth, power, and privilege, and how they are shared within a given society;
- (ii) "**social class**" processes, focusing on the ordering of people according to their imputed worth and by means of such terms as class, stratum and rank; and
- (iii) **mobility** processes dealing with the movement of individuals or groups across and/or within ranked positions.

Social status is thus one's position in a social hierarchy or stratification. It is also the relative level of social value a person is considered to possess. Such social value includes respect, honour, assumed competence, and deference (en.m.wikipedia.org/wikipedia).

The Status of Youths in Nigeria

Though they were *lumpen zoon politicon*s prior to their access to political power, most of the old time youths enjoyed upward mobility as they had their status enhanced through their access to power right from colonial time to post-colonial era, and had therefore become *embourgeoisised*. They enjoyed status symbols that include latest and expensive

products in town like cars, private aircraft, speed-boats, houses, embroidered cloths, ornaments, televisions, titles and honours including traditional and religious titles as well as university honorary degrees/doctorates/professorships (Adekanye, 1993). This resulted from the kind of formal education received which recognized 'how much' the individual can consume with whatever s/he accumulates rather than what s/he can create (Olutayo, 2018). This is apart from the fact that they enjoyed free schooling and sumptuous jobs which were available after living school. This could have accounted for the reason why Hammed (2024) stated that apart from 1966 civil war, Nigeria used to be relatively calm and devoid of extremely violent activities.

Meanwhile, when formal education started in Nigeria, it was to meet the need to provide workers for government and private establishments that arose during colonialism. Then, the knowledge was to secure a certificate for government employment but however began to recede with the introduction of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) of 1987 which had, as part of its conditionality, rolling back of the state. This is seen in the changing welfare system, job creation, housing policy, transportation and other infrastructures that are insufficient to absorb the youths. Unfortunately, the private sector that could provide succour also depended on the 'receding' government for survival (Okunola, 2013; Olutayo, 2018). Moreover, Nigeria is one of the countries with highest fertility and mortality rates in the world. This affects not only population growth but also the welfare of the people. This prevents Nigeria from enjoying demographic dividend, that is, accelerated growth that may result from a decline in a country's mortality and fertility and the subsequent change in the age structure of the population (Olaniran, 2018). The implication of this is the increasing population of youths amidst declining socio-economic resources. Hence, there is the declining welfare of young population.

However, the situation couldn't have been that worse but for politicians' (old youths) perpetration and perpetuation of corruption leading to massive pauperization of the majority of the citizens, mostly new youths, not having opportunities to get gainful

employment through their certificates, and which has made Nigeria to be regarded poverty capital of the world having taken over from India (Mailafia, 2019).

In some countries, politicians pay for private things they enjoy while in government. Gary Walters, a former White House Chief of Staff, said, "All those things that are personal in nature that we all pay for, the first family pays for" (Kperogi, 2020). But these are occasions for subsidy in Nigeria through the concentric circle that involve the elected officials – President, Vice President, Ministers, members of the National Assembly, Governors, Deputy Governors, Commissioners, members of State Assemblies, local council officials and the numberless coterie of aids and hangers-on and so on (Kperogi, 2020). The last but not the least is the fact that they are very corrupt and never wanting to leave the political space for youths to take over contrary to juxtaposing or comparable experiences in other nations. Sabastian Kurz of Austria became Chancellor at the age of 31, Emmanuel Macron emerged as French President at age 39 and Prime Minister Justin Trudeau of Canada got to office at age 45 (Adeleke and Subaru, 2022). The old youths in power continue to expand their privileges leading to high cost of governance through ostentatious life style. They engage in embezzlement and misappropriation of public funds, stashing away of Nigerian resources through money laundering. This is as a result of money becoming main criterion of social ranking creating tendencies towards insatiable acquisitiveness, excessive primitive accumulation, avariciousness, conspicuous consumption and self-seeking (Adekanye, 1993). What followed was pauperization of many, including the new youths.

Unfortunately, when new youths make demands for improvements in their welfare, as their status became inconsistent with that of the old youths, who enjoyed upward social mobility at their youthful time, the old youths called the new youths a lazy set of people. At a Commonwealth meeting, former President Mohammed Buhari, derided new youths by declaring them lazy people who feel entitled to free things because Nigeria is a rich oil producing nation. To him, they do not go to school, they do not work, they just simply laze around expecting the

government to provide answers to all their difficulties (Nwakanama, 2018). Moreover, while the government failed in arresting the upsurge in Boko Haram insurgency, kidnappings, murders, armed robberies and suicides, it ran after youths who had become bored of joblessness, stigmatization as "lazy youths" and "yahoo boys" (Ozekhome, 2020).

According to Section 16 (1b) and 16 (2C) of 1999 Nigerian Constitution, the economic objective of Nigerian State is to *run the economy in a manner as to secure maximum welfare, freedom and happiness of every citizen on the basis of social justice and equality of status and opportunity and that the economic system is not operated in such a manner as to permit concentration of wealth or the means of production and exchange in the hands of few individuals or a group of people*, Nigerian politicians run Nigerian economy in the typical sense of Merriam-Webster Dictionary's definition of a politician as a person primarily interested in political office for selfish or other narrow, usually shortsighted reasons. According to Adegboruwa (2020:32), Nigerian politician

will only devise clever means of siphoning money, put all his family expenses on the state revenue and begin to live larger than life. And not having performed to implement any agenda for the development of his people, he is afraid to go back to his original base, where there is no power supply, there is no water, no hospital, no schools and virtually nothing to make life meaningful. So, he has to steal enough money that he considers sufficient to last himself and his family their lifetime, enough to supply power, enough to hire and maintain armed policemen, enough to send his children abroad for their education, having refused to pay local teachers well and caused them to embrace constant strikes that rubbish the education calendar...

The consequence of this is poor socio-economic conditions of the people, especially new youths, who are made to experience no enjoyment of constant electricity, clean water, decent public housing, entitlement programmes, student loan, access to credit

and loans to build their businesses, no jobs and no benefit from oil (Nwakanma, 2018). Nigerian politicians don't have empathy for fellow citizens, having their mentality damaged by power as they don't share people's pains, perpetrate abuse of power and promote unpopular causes. As such, they dwarf the citizens, especially new youths who are the nation's present and future. Meanwhile, *"a State which dwarfs its men in order that they may be docile in its hands, even for beneficial purpose, will find that with small men no great things can be achieved"* (Mill, 1920 cited in Ayoade, 1997). They don't show empathy for the citizens (Kperogi, 2019). They do this because they don't have community sense.

However, new youths cannot totally exculpate themselves from the cumulative oppression that plunged them to the present socio-economic predicament. Many a time, youths supported the nation's exploiters perhaps for want of material gains. When life became solitary, poor, nasty, brutish and short under General Sani Abacha's maximum rule, certain youths gave their support for the elongation of General Sani Abacha in government through a phantom organization called Youths Earnestly Ask for Abacha (YEAA) under the leadership of Daniel Kanu, demanding General Abacha to stand for election as President in 1998 (Ayoade, 1997; <https://en.wikipedia.org>). Also, in Nigeria's fourth republic, there have been cases of youths being used as thugs and ready made army by politicians both at executive and legislative levels to protect their own selfish interests and centrifugal forces (Okunola, 2013). There are even instances when youths used violent enactments against themselves by wielding machetes, guns and other dangerous weapons and chasing, wounding and hacking down themselves based on gangsterism and/or cultism (Hammed, 2024). In addition, instead of engaging in activism which used to be initiation to social justice activism that borders on government, democracy, human rights, social justice and other noble ideals, most of Nigerian new youths have effectively dissociated mentally from Nigeria as they now turn their discernments to entertainment, gossip, comedy, football, and petty fights on the social media. (Kperogi, 2020). In fact, not all youths

are energetic and contented, many are lazy and greedy (Olalekan, 2020).

New Youths' Reactions to Status Inconsistency

The inability of the Nigerian new youths to enjoy upward social mobility like the old youths pointed to the fact that youths suffered status inconsistency and they began to challenge it. New youths compare themselves to old youths, through possession of political power and the privileges it accrued to its holders. They realized old youths benefitted a lot from power compared to new youths. This is a sense of symbolized inferiority. They began to make demands on Nigeria for power to reverse the trend. There are various ways by which groups react to symbolized inferiority, according to Tumin (1967):

- (i) The group may reject standards by which its members are evaluated, and insist on substituting other standards that will secure for members a much higher and more positive social evaluation.
- (ii) The group may spend extravagant amounts of money on the purchase of symbols of status.
- (iii) The group may seek to denigrate those who denigrate it and reject them as judges, while it retains its the standards by which their judgments are made.
- (iv) The group may reject altogether the society whose values and standards denigrate it, and make war upon that society in the form of deviant behaviour, political attack, or even revolution.

In reacting to status inconsistency, the new youths have employed certain strategies that appear conforming to some of the yardsticks stated above. For the first approach of Tumin (1967), they have sought for instituting wider space for themselves in government so that they too can raise their status like the old youths through 'Not too Young to Run' campaign that culminated in 'Not too Young to Run Act' of April 2018. The law reduced the ages for elective positions for State House of Assembly and House of Representatives from 30 years to 25 years, Senate and Governorship from 35 years to 30 years and office of the

President from 40 to 30 years (Adeleke and Folarin, 2024).

The Tumin's second technique is not presently mush on ground for the new youths, given that most of them are not gainfully employed and are therefore poor. However, there is the appearance that some of them now use their little money or family one to emigrate the country for getting greener pastures abroad due to their dissatisfaction with the state of the nation, high level of insecurity, unemployment, infrastructural deficit and hunger so that they can live their desired lives and achieve their dreams as they gained enhanced status through hard currency they remit home. Some desperate Nigerian youths who failed to migrate even entered other countries through illegal means without necessary documents (Tugbiyele, 2024).

For the third approach, they organized protests across some cities of Nigeria, with the harsh tag #EndSARS. Nigerian youths, through the aid of social media, mobilized themselves for spontaneous protests against the brutality of the SARS organ of the Nigeria Police and the government yielded to their request for the suspension of its operations. Interpretatively, #EndSARS protest though targeted the eradication of police brutality, but symbolically, it was organized to eliminate socio-economic inequalities, poor civil and political rights, and re-surfacing of government corruption (Ogunyemi, 2020). They used the protest to reject the stigmatization of being called "lazy youths" and "yahoo boys" being displayed as diadems of the government's war against corruption achievements (Ozekhome, 2020). They referred to themselves as the 'Soro Soke' generation that wanted their desire to be heard and their passion for change (Hammed, 2024).

They have also applied the method of radical mobilization which conforms to Tumin's fourth technique of rejecting status inconsistency. Many of the Nigerian youths have been indoctrinated, especially in the Northeast, by radical clerics that their endemic poverty and limited opportunities for upward social mobility is political in nature. Thus, there have been, apart from similar other groups, Maitasine during the third Republic and Boko Haram insurgency in the

fourth Republic (Hammed, 2024). The Niger Delta people, mostly of new youths, have also radically responded to the injustice displayed by the Nigerian government over the use of proceeds from oil and gas exploration in the Niger Delta. In this instance, there have been Niger Delta Avengers (NDA), Ultimate Warriors of Niger Delta (UWND), Adaka Boro Avengers (ABA), Reformed Egbesu Boys (REB), and the Niger Delta Greenland Justice (NDGJ) that blew up the 32 inch Effurun-Otor delivery line operated by NNPC in Delta State (Adeleke, 2020).

It is therefore reasonable to state that youths engage in both *live off comfort* and *live for comfort* in their reactions to public affairs. They *live off comfort* when they engage in activities or causes that tend to change political oppression and tyranny against themselves and/ or the people generally without minding what will cost them. This manifested in #EndSARS protesters' 'You See This Time 'We Die Here Today'. Of course, many of them died in the process but banning of SARS was achieved. The youths, through Bayelsa Partnership Initiative, also advocated against militancy in the Niger Delta bill board messages like 'We are youths, the future of Bayelsa: Don't Give Us Guns, Give Us Jobs' (Ikporukpo, 2007). Of course, relaxation of tension or relative peace in the Niger Delta cannot be unconnected with cooperation of new youths with the government of Nigeria. They *live for comfort* when they engage in activities that benefit them only or part of them materially against the welfare of some of them or general welfare of the society. A typical example is *2 Million Man Match* of Daniel Kanu's Youths Earnestly Ask for Abacha in spite of Abacha's records of human rights violations, done for personal aggrandizement of Daniel Kanu and his cohorts on the movement.

The argument above corroborates Osaghae's (1994) observation that some people get involved in politics to contribute to the development of their society while some get involved for the purpose of actualizing themselves in terms of status, respect and the like.

Socio-Economic Implications of 'New' Youths' Reactions to Status Inconsistency

Financial remittance is associated with emigration as it helps to stimulate the economy, improve gross national income, create job opportunities in various sectors, enhance families' standards and provide capital for national growth and development (Tugbiyele, 2024). Many however just said good bye to Nigeria as a result of the prevalence of insecurity across the length and breadth of Nigeria as some who returned home have been abducted and killed, serving as deterrent to other willing ones. Through this, Nigerian State suffers brain drain as skilled ones who refuse to return home create skill shortages and gaps in the critical sectors of the economy like Health, Banking, Engineering and Academia (Aladetoyinbo, 2023; Tugbiyele, 2024).

Bad policies are associated with bad government. Bad government violates basic human rights of the citizens, promotes corruption and kills proper accountability. This engenders dissatisfaction, especially among the youths who find their energy and dynamism being damaged by the government. Consequently, many of 'new' youths became maladjusted, face a desire to be rich and raise their status, get involved in many social vices like kidnapping, cybercrimes, oil theft, vandalism, armed robbery, property destruction, increased unrest and electoral violence (Aladejebi, 2024). For the female ones, many of them ventured into human trafficking for sex and work in European countries like Italy, Spain, Belgium, Norway, United Kingdom, Sweden and Germany (Aderinto, 2019). Many of the young people who venture into these crimes do so because of frustration after fruitless searches for non-existent jobs coupled with mounting responsibilities to handle (Obariagbon and Aderinto, 2017). All these dent the nation's image in the comity of nations.

There have also been destructions of lives and properties. Several protesters were killed by security operatives and military, and both private and public properties were destroyed by protesters during the #EndSars protest. There were also disruptions of movements and looting and vandalisation of shops in Lagos State (<https://ijsm.net.>article>download>). The historic and famous

Igbosere High Court that once served as Supreme Court was burnt down during #EndSars protest in October 2020 (punchng.com). It was also revealed by the then Inspector General of Police, Mohammed Adamu, that not less than 22 Police Officers were killed by youths protesting police brutality while hundreds of Police Station and formations were damaged across the country during the protest (<https://www.premiumtimesng.com>). Over 100 civilian deaths were given burial for #EndSARS movement (<https://www.africanews.com>). Television Continental and Max FM broadcast stations, including vehicles belonging to their workers, were razed by irate youths through #EndSARS protest. The broadcast stations were linked to Bola Hammed Tinubu who was, at that time, the National Leader of All Progressives Congress (premiumtimesng.com).

The effects of rising insecurity and declining foreign direct investment are also there. Radical or violent enactments by the youths to challenge the status quo or in-fights among themselves cause human rights abuses, political instability among other security implications (Hammed, 2024). A lot of positive economic externalities associated with Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) are being repelled as most foreign companies quit or some refuse to come to Nigeria since some of the expatriates are being exposed to dangers by taking them as hostages through youth's violence reactions to their status inconsistency (Ikporukpo, 2007). Positive economic externalities like filling of skill gap between the rich and poor countries, filling of capital flows to cushion both internal and external gaps and technology transfers and spillover capital are being lost by Nigeria to the advantage of other developing nations that are relatively peaceful (Yusuff, 2003).

Conclusion

The corrupt attitude of most 'old' youths who have had access to political power has made the vocation of politics in Nigeria tended towards Max Weber's *live off politics* instead of *live for politics* and created antagonistic reactions from the 'new' youths with its consequent negative outcomes, socially, economically and politically. The negative effects of the reactions of new youths to status

inconsistency have greased neither the old youths nor new youths. Also, it has never been positive for the sustainable development of Nigeria. Both the corrupt activities of the old youths in government that culminated in the impoverishment of the citizens and radical reactions from the new youths to eradicate their inhibition to upward social mobility hinder the sustainable socio-economic development of Nigeria. There is therefore the need for the development of what philosophers call 'epistemic virtues' like careful and attentive reasoning, openness to evidence and critical reasoning (Olutayo, 2018). This is a case of *t'omode basubu, awo 'waju, b'agba ba subu, a wehin wo*, which is translated to imply that the youths look at the front when they fall down while the old look at the back when they fall. In resolving Nigeria's development problem, as the understanding of the past is important so is the consideration of the future necessary, when our target is attaining sustainable development. Appreciation of both will make epistemic steps of today correct the errors of the past in order to avoid its recurrence in the future. The essence is to build the historical reality of social imagination and action that link past with the present to launch a future inbuilt with higher level of freedom and happiness for the majority of the people, if truly the purpose of government is the happiness of the people.

Suggestions

To make people take vocation of politics as *live for politics* in Nigeria, the following suggestions are offered. It is important to reorganize that all our socialization agencies view and preach the understanding of the totality of human experience in man's environment in Nigeria. Our socialisation should seek for holistic understanding of the environment incorporating the knowledge to exploit and the wisdom to distribute. There is need to develop the epistemic virtue of collectively exploiting the socio-economic resources made available by our environment and commonly distribute them. We need to learn from Mahatma Ghandi of India who says: "The world has enough for everyone's need, but not for everyone's greed" (quoted in Kperogi, 2020:32) in order to prevent cases of

antagonistic relations among various individuals and groups in Nigeria.

There is need for youth movement. The new youth need to take a clue from nationalists who made resilient struggle to attain political independence. They need concerted and sustained effort to reach the stardom. All particularities which make some of them *live for politics* should be avoided. They need to unite themselves not for becoming *lumpen bourgeoisies*, but welfarists who do not use socio-political opportunities available to them for preserving and perpetuating exploitation of state resources as their subsidies, if Nigeria is to be relatively peaceful to attain sustainable development.

New youths should realize that the era jobs waiting for graduates is over as the introduction of SAP has compelled the rolling back of the state. Youths should be educated for their social needs. They should school not for government work but for applying their knowledge to resolve their socio-economic challenges especially job opportunities in form of self-employment. Education should not be for paper certificate but application of knowledge acquired in school to solve societal problems.

One other epistemic virtue is the development of community sense embodied in moral asceticism by the old and new youths. This can be achieved through the embrace of (i) universal golden rule which invites us to doing unto others what we expect from others; second, (2) the logic of utilitarianism that claims that our actions are right if they advance the happiness of others and reduces their pains, and thirdly, (3) the rule of humanity that stresses preserving human life, demonstrating compassion for others and sympathy as essence of life. The old youths who have access to power and even the new youths who may have it in future should begin to think of tribulations and vicissitudes of life like natural disasters, injuries, sickness, accidents, property damage, economic losses and poverty as no condition is permanent.

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